

SIMULATION OF PROGRESIVE DAMAGE IN OPEN-HOLE COMPOSITE SPECIMENS: NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION

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Keywords: Damage Progression, Open-Hole, Cohesive Zone Model

ABSTRACT

The tensile response of $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$ and $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ IM7/977-3 carbon/epoxy open-hole coupons is simulated using two numerical approaches. In the first approach, matrix cracking and delamination are modeled using a-priori insertion of cohesive interfaces to the model, where the second approach utilizes the regularized extended finite element method for adaptive insertion of the cohesive interfaces during the run. A numerical investigation is carried in which the number of cohesive interfaces is varied within the finite-element models. It was shown that matrix cracking plays a dominant role in the failure process of these laminates and should thus be accounted for in the finite element analysis, with higher cohesive crack density yielding a more realistic prediction of failure.

1 INTRODUCTION

The application of composite materials in structural aerospace applications often requires the presence of holes, which can lead to stress concentration and initiation of damage within the material. This raises the necessity to develop an efficient numerical methodology that can successfully predict the influence of these structural discontinuities on the performance envelope of the structure.

During the last decades, numerous numerical approaches have been applied in an attempt to predict the behavior of open-hole composite coupons under tensile and compressive loads. It was demonstrated that a combination of cohesive zone models together with continuum damage modeling techniques, allowed capturing the evolution of damage around the hole during the loading process, as well as predict the global stress-strain response of the specimen, under static [1]–[3] and fatigue loading conditions [4-5]

Two modeling approaches were separately utilized in order to numerically predict damage propagation in $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$ and $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ IM7/977-3 carbon/epoxy open-hole coupons subjected to tensile and compressive loads. In the first approach, matrix cracking and delamination are modeled using a-priori insertion of cohesive interfaces to the model, where the second approach utilizes the regularized extended finite element method for adaptive insertion of the cohesive interfaces during the run. A numerical investigation is carried, in which dominant numerical parameters are varied. In particular, matrix crack spacing and position will be examined. The numerical results are compared to the experimental data, both in terms of the predicted stress vs. strain behavior, as well the damage propagation at selected points along the loading path.

2 PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

Open-Hole tensile experiments, described in detail in [4], were used as a benchmark for the numerical simulation approaches presented here. The open-hole specimen's were fabricated using unidirectional IM7/977-3 prepregs, having $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$ and $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ layups, with an average 0.127 mm cured ply thickness. The specimen's geometry, having a total length is 250mm, is shown in Figure 1. Tapered aluminum tabs were bonded to the end of the specimens in order to apply the tensile load, yielding a gauge length of 138 mm. A tensile load was applied to the specimens at a rate of 2 mm/min. Strains were measured using an external extensometer having a gage length of a 25.4 mm, located at the center of the specimen. The basic lamina properties are listed in Table 1, together with the mode-I and mode-II interlaminar properties. The non-linear in-plane shear vs. shear strain response is brought in Figure 2.

Figure 1 – Open Hole specimen geometry [4]

Property	Symbol	Value
Tensile longitudinal modulus [GPa]	E_{1T}	164
Compressive longitudinal modulus [GPa]	E_{1C}	137
Tensile transverse modulus [GPa]	E_{2T}	8.98
Compressive transverse modulus [GPa]	E_{2C}	8.69
Tensile longitudinal strength [MPa]	X_T	2,905
Compressive longitudinal strength [MPa]	X_C	1,569
Tensile transverse strength [MPa]	Y_T	78.9
Compressive transverse strength [MPa]	Y_C	248
Tensile longitudinal failure strain [%]	ϵ_{1T}	1.91
Compressive longitudinal failure strain [%]	ϵ_{1C}	1.28
Compressive transverse failure strain [%]	ϵ_{2C}	3.12
In-plane shear modulus [GPa]	G_{12}	5.01
In-plane shear strength at 0.2% offset [MPa]	$F_{0.2\%}^0$	57.9
In-plane shear strength at 5% shear strain [MPa]	$F_{5\%}^0$	99.4
Major Poisson's ratio	ν_{12}	0.320
Mode-I strain energy release rate [J/m^2]	G_{IC}	256
Mode-II strain energy release rate [J/m^2]	G_{IIC}	650

Table 1 – Lamina material properties [4]

3 NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

3.1 A Priori Inserted Cohesive Interfaces

Using this modeling approach, a continuum damage model is combined together with discrete cohesive models to explicitly describe each of the dominant failure modes within the laminate: matrix cracking, fiber damage, and delamination. A detailed finite element model, in which each ply was explicitly described using thick-shell elements, was implemented in the commercial LS-DYNA finite element code (Figure 3). The whole coupon geometry was modeled in terms of in-plane dimension, half-model was modeled in the out-of-plane dimension due to symmetry condition (Figure 3 shows the specimen mirrored with respect to the y-x plane). Based on experience gained when modeling fracture of a similar material system, a typical element size of 0.3 mm was chosen. In each ply, the finite element mesh was oriented parallel to the fiber direction. In order to capture in-plane matrix splitting, solid cohesive elements having a zero thickness were inserted in each ply parallel to the fiber direction, with 0.6 mm interval between the cohesive element rows (Figure 4). The resulting model included approximately 1,100,000 elements in total.

Figure 2 – Experimental in-plane shear vs. shear strain response of IM7/977-3 UD prepreg

Figure 3 – Isometric view of an open-hole specimen finite element model. Each laminate ply is explicitly modeled using LS-DYNA's thick-shell elements.

Figure 4 – Lines representing rows of solid cohesive elements in the $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ open-hole coupon. a). A close look at a single 60° ply. b). Transparent view of the finite element mesh, showing cohesive paths in all of the laminate plies.

In order to capture homogenized in-plane damage, LS-DYNA's material model number 58 (*MAT_LAMINATED_COMPOSITE_FABRIC) [6] was applied to the thick shell elements. Using this material model, stress rises until the ultimate strength value is reached. Additional strain applied to the material will result in strength reduction until complete failure is reached. The model allows non-linear description of shear in the in-plane direction, but this limits the failure model to exhibit a flat-faceted failure envelope, with no coupling between the various failure modes. The material model incorporates a minimum stress limit factor after maximum stress is reached. The minimum stress values were set based on fracture energy values of 175 and 17 KJ/m² for the fiber and matrix, respectively. For more details regarding the material behavior, the reader is referred to [6].

Both in-plane matrix splitting and delamination were modeled using bilinear cohesive law with mode interaction. For matrix splitting, LS-DYNA's *MAT_COHESIVE_GENERAL was applied, using its default parameters for mode interaction. LS-DYNA's cohesive tiebreak contact algorithm was applied in order to capture delamination damage. For both in-plane splitting and delamination, cohesive contact stiffness of 5,000 N/mm³ was applied, which is typical of a resin-rich epoxy layer having a thickness of 0.01 mm [7].

Figure 5 – Numerical representation of the dominant damage mechanisms within the laminate: a) homogenized in-plane damage using LS-DYNA's material model number 58; b) Matrix splitting is modeled using solid cohesive elements; c) Delamination is modeled using LS-DYNA's tiebreak contact algorithm.

Figure 5 summarizes the different numerical techniques used in order to capture the dominant damage mechanisms within the laminate: Homogenized in-plane damage using LS-DYNA's material model number 58, discrete matrix splits using solid cohesive elements and *MAT_COHESIVE_GENERAL, and delamination using LS-DYNA's cohesive tiebreak contact.

In order to apply the tensile load in the analysis, a prescribed displacement constraint was applied to aluminum tabs which were attached to the coupon using LS-DYNA's tied contact algorithm. The numerical solution was performed using LS-DYNA's explicit integration scheme, with an approximate

solution time of 30 minutes using 60 CPU's.

The predicted load vs. displacement results for $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ and $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$ layups is presented in Figure 6. The experimental results are colored in light grey, where the experimental average is colored using a black dashed line. For the $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ layup, the simulation prediction slightly over-estimates the load with respect to the experimental data. For the $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$ layup, the predicted response is higher than the experimental average, but is within the bounds of the highest experimental response.

Figure 6 – Numerical and experimental stress vs. strain results, obtained for (a) $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ and (b) $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$ layups

The numerically predicted damage within each ply at 90% of the maximum load, is presented vs. the experimental CT scan results for both $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$ and $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ layups in Figure 7 and Figure 8, respectively. In general, the numerically predicted damage matches the experimental findings. The high density of the cohesive interfaces allows capturing the matrix cracks within the plies. As expected, matrix cracking covered larger volumes of material within the soft laminate, compared to the hard laminate which is dominated by fiber failure.

Figure 7 – Intralaminar damage for $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ layup at 90% of the maximum load- simulation results vs. CT scans [5]

Figure 8 - Intralaminar damage for $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$ layup at 90% of the maximum load – simulation results vs. CT scans [5]

In order to investigate the effect of the number of the cohesive interfaces on the results, a series of numerical models was built (Figure 9). The baseline model presented in Figure 9 is identical to the model described in the above section. The models for Cases A, B, C, and D included cohesive interfaces with decreasing density – in Case A, the cohesive crack density was reduced by 50% relative to the cohesive crack density of the baseline model. In Case B, four rows of cohesive elements were located parallel to the fiber direction in each ply, with two rows tangent to the central hole in the coupon, and an additional row of cohesive element spaced 1.2 mm from the first. Case C was similar to Case B, but with the rows of elements further away from the whole being removed (i.e., only rows of tangent cohesive elements remained in the model). In Case D, no cohesive elements were present within the plies. For all cases, A to D, delamination was accounted for using the interlaminar cohesive contact. For Case E, the coupon is modeled using a single thick shell element through its thickness (i.e.; no cohesive interfaces are present in the model, including delamination).

Figure 9 – Numerical models of $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ layup having decreasing number of cohesive interfaces

The predicted load vs. displacement results obtained from the simulation for $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ and $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$ layups is presented in Figure 10. For the $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ layup, which is dominated by the matrix behavior, reducing the number of cohesive interfaces results in a global stiffness increase. This behavior is expected, as the presence of the cohesive interfaces introduces some compliance to the

structure. This behavior was less pronounced in the $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$ layup which is dominated by the fiber stiffness and is less effected by the matrix behavior. The highest over-prediction of the maximum strength as well as the structural compliance was obtained for Case E (where the coupon was modeled using a single through-thickness thick shell element). It seems as the absence of matrix cracking, together with the limitation of the flat-faceted failure envelope which was used in the analysis, failed to account for dominant failure modes which governed the experimental behavior.

Figure 10 - Numerical and experimental stress vs. strain results, obtained for (a) $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ and (b) $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$ layups, for models having varying numbers of cohesive interfaces.

The final failure Mode of the $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ and of $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$ layups obtained for all of the cases tested, is brought in Figure 11 and Figure 12, respectively. For the $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ layup, results obtained using the baseline model, together with results obtained from models tested in Case A, B, and C, were in reasonable agreement with the experimental failure mode. For Case D, failure in the simulation initiated under the aluminum tabs. For Case E, failure was exhibited by a single crack that initiated from the hole to both side of the coupon, an obvious result given the limitation of the model and lack of cohesive interfaces. For the $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$ layup, results obtained from all models were with reasonable agreement with the experimental failure mode. Better agreement was obtained from models with higher number of cohesive interfaces, as they allowed a more realistic description of the matrix cracks within the coupon.

Figure 11 - Final failure mode of $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ layup for numerical models having different number of cohesive interfaces. For the Baseline, A, B and C model, the top row images are normal to the external ply of the specimen. The bottom row of these images are seen in transparent view, showing all plies within the laminate.

Figure 12 - Final failure mode of $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$ layup for numerical models having different number of cohesive interfaces. For the Baseline, A, B, and C models, the top row images are normal to the external ply of the specimen. The bottom row of these images are seen in transparent view, showing all plies within the laminate.

3.2 Regularized Extended Finite Element Method

Discrete Damage Modeling (DDM) represents an approach to progressive failure modeling in composites whereby multiple individual damage events such as matrix cracks and delamination are explicitly introduced (via a failure criteria) into the model and are represented by displacement discontinuities as seen in realistic failure processes. The DDM methodology employed in section 3.2 is based on a Regularized eXtended Finite Element Technique (Rx-FEM) [8] implemented into the research code BSAM [9]. A cohesive interface formulation is used for delamination and Rx-FEM propagation. Multiple cracking in each ply is allowed and crack spacing is limited by the fineness of the mesh or a user-specified parameter.

Fiber failure in BSAM is addressed in two manners, one progressive and one catastrophic. Progressive fiber failure is modeled via a modified version of the property degradation approach described in [10], for fibers only. This approach is not employed herein. Catastrophic failure in tensile loading is accomplished via the critical failure volume (CFV) method, which allows for the ability to locate the most probable failure region in composites with a non-uniform stress distribution bounded by an iso-stress contour of the fiber direction stress [11]. The CFV method has proven to be effective where fiber failure on the ply-level coincides with final failure. CFV was used to evaluate fiber failure in the models described in section 3.2.

One feature of the Rx-FEM implementation within BSAM is that the crack spacing is limited to a minimum of 6 elements between cracks. This is shown, with an example mesh, in Figure 13. In this figure, a series of cracks are shown in a 90° ply. Due to the nature of a radial mesh, finer crack spacing is allowed near the hole edge, presumably where it is most important. Similarly to the study described in Section 3.1, a series of different cases were examined where minimum crack spacing is increased from the baseline, 6-element spacing to no cracks. Table 2 describes these cases.

Figure 13 - Example laminate mesh and single ply mesh with crack spacing of 6 elements.

	Case A	Case B	Case C	Case D
Matrix Cracks	6-element spacing	48-element spacing	2 cracks per ply	no cracks
Delamination	yes	yes	yes	yes
Fiber Failure	CFV in 0° or 30°	CFV in 0° or 30°	CFV in 0° or 30°	CFV in 0° or 30°

Table 2: description of simulation cases conducted in section 3.2.

As in Section 3.1, simulation results were compared with experimental data obtained from [5]. In that work, 3 stacking sequences were tested in open-hole tension and compression. Figure 14 and Figure 15 shows the BSAM simulation results from Case A model configurations compared with experimentally obtained X-Ray micro-CT results for the $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ and $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$, respectively. In general, the simulated damage patterns match the experimental damage patterns relatively well, especially for the quasi-isotropic layup. However, even with the finest crack spacing of Case A, the density of predicted cracking is not approaching that observed in the experiments.

Figure 14: Matrix damage for $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ layup at 90% of the maximum load, Case A (crack spacing 6) vs. experiment

Figure 15: Close-up view of matrix damage for $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$ layup at 90% of the maximum load, case A (crack spacing 6) vs. experiment.

Predicted stress-strain behavior for all cases is compared with experimentally observed stress-strain behavior obtained from 5 replicated tests for each stacking sequence. The experimental failure mode for the $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ layup was through extensive delamination and matrix crack linkage, with some fiber breakage occurring at final specimen separation. The failure of the $[0/45/90/-15]_{2s}$ specimens, however occurred due to fiber failure cascading across the specimen catastrophically. Final experimental failure loads averaged 409 MPa for the $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ layup and 554 MPa for the $[0/45/90/-15]_{2s}$ layup. Simulation results indicated catastrophic fiber failure in all cases except Case A for the $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ layup which showed massive delamination-crack linkage followed by a load-drop. Transparent views of all matrix damage for both stacking sequences are shown in Figure 17 and Figure 18. In these figures is also listed the peak load and the resulting failure mode.

Figure 16: Stress-strain behavior from experiment and all model cases for the (a) $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ layup and the (b) $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$ layup.

Figure 17: Transparent view of the predicted matrix damage (delamination and cracking) for each simulation case for the $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ layup. Note that the experimental failure mode was through delamination-crack linkages and occurred on average at 409 MPa.

Figure 18: Transparent, close-up view of the predicted matrix damage (delamination and cracking) for each simulation case for the $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$ layup. Note that the experimental failure mode was through catastrophic fiber failure and occurred on average at 554 MPa.

It is important to discuss the role of matrix cracking on failure loads and modes observed in the modeling. The key feature of matrix crack and delamination interaction near a notch is the reduction in fiber-direction stresses. This is especially clear in the $[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$ layup (see Figure 18) where a single crack on each side of the hole in the 0 ply results in a large increase in predicted strength when compared with Case D containing no cracks. This is also evident in the predicted failure-mode shift from delamination to fiber failure in the $[30/60/90/-60/-30]_{2s}$ layup (see

Figure 17). In this layup, the 30 ply experiences relatively high fiber stresses, which in Case A are relieved enough to allow a delamination and crack network to form and cause failure. In Cases B-D, the statistical fiber failure criteria, CFV, is triggered before such a network can form due to the higher stress concentration at the hole edges caused by fewer, stress-relieving matrix cracks.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Numerical simulations were carried in order to predict the tensile behavior of open-hole carbon epoxy laminates. It was shown that matrix cracking plays a dominant role in the failure process of the layups simulated, and should thus be accounted for in the finite element analysis, with higher cohesive crack

density yielding a more realistic behavior. Interlaminar cohesive interfaces accounting for delamination, combined with rows of cohesive elements tangent to the hole, were able to capture the dominant failure modes and stress vs. strain behavior. This finding is important, given the numerical complexity and the efforts required to generate models containing a priori inserted cohesive interfaces, and emphasizes the benefits of X-FEM which gives freedom of crack placement allowing for ease of modeling transverse matrix cracking.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support from the US Air Force Research Laboratory and Rafael Advanced Defense Systems LTD.

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